

Comparative Analysis of Postoperative Complications in Total Abdominal Vs. Vaginal Hysterectomy: At the General Hospital of Cancun "Dr. Jesús Kumate Rodríguez" (January–December 2024)

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ABSTRACT

Background: Hysterectomy is one of the most frequently performed gynecological procedures worldwide and is a fundamental intervention in the management of numerous benign and malignant uterine conditions. The choice of surgical approach—abdominal, vaginal, laparoscopic, or robotic—is a critical aspect of gynecological practice, as each approach carries a different profile of risks, complications, and recovery times.

Objective: To compare the frequency and type of postoperative complications between abdominal hysterectomy and vaginal hysterectomy in patients treated at the General Hospital of Cancun "Dr. Jesús Kumate Rodríguez", in order to generate local evidence that allows improving surgical safety and guiding institutional practice.

Materials and methods : This was an observational, retrospective, comparative, and cross-sectional study with a quantitative approach. Clinical records of all patients who underwent total hysterectomy via the abdominal or vaginal route between January and December 2024 were analyzed.

Results: A total of 78 cases of patients undergoing hysterectomy were obtained according to the surgical route —abdominal and vaginal—, the final group was 67 patients included in the analysis. The largest proportion of cases were abdominal hysterectomies, with 92.5% of the group also having the highest number of surgical complications. In contrast, the vaginal route accounts for a smaller number of procedures with 7.5% having clearly identified complications (one post-surgical hematoma and one case of urinary retention).

Conclusions: When comparing the frequency and type of postoperative complications between abdominal and vaginal hysterectomy in patients treated at the Hospital, the evidence shows that, among abdominal complications, the most frequent were bladder injury and urinary incontinence. Despite being the most frequently used approach, the majority of abdominal procedures were uncomplicated (55 cases), reflecting an acceptable relative safety rate.

KEYWORDS: abdominal hysterectomy, vaginal hysterectomy, complications, associated factors

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INTRODUCTION

Hysterectomy is one of the most frequently performed gynecological procedures worldwide and constitutes a fundamental intervention in the management of multiple benign and malignant uterine pathologies (1). The choice of surgical route—abdominal, vaginal, laparoscopic, or robotic—represents a critical aspect of gynecological practice, as each approach carries a different profile of risks, complications, and recovery times. The decision regarding the technique depends on factors such as uterine size and mobility, gynecological history, comorbidities, technological availability, and surgeon experience (2).

Abdominal hysterectomy remains the most widely used technique in hospitals in developing countries due to its utility in cases complex and to the extensive experience accumulated with this route. However, it is associated with greater surgical aggression, increased postoperative pain, a high risk of surgical site infection, visceral injury, and longer hospital stays (3). In contrast, vaginal hysterectomy is considered the safest alternative for properly selected benign pathologies, featuring less intraoperative bleeding, faster recovery, lower risk of infection, and shorter hospital stays. Nonetheless, its use is often limited by a shortage of personnel trained in this technique rather than clinical contraindications (4).

Recent literature reinforces these findings. A systematic review of 44 studies concluded that the occurrence of intra- and postoperative complications depends on the type of approach, body mass index, and surgical experience, highlighting that the vaginal route and minimally invasive techniques offer better outcomes when clinically viable (5). In the national context, a study conducted in Mexico reported that, although there is a growing trend toward the use of laparoscopic techniques, the abdominal route still accounts for approximately 39% of cases and is associated with a complication rate of 10%, which is higher than that observed in vaginal and laparoscopic approaches (6). This variation reflects a significant gap between international recommendations—which point to the vaginal route as the first option for most benign pathologies—and daily practice in public institutions where educational, technical, and structural limitations persist.

The comparative analysis between abdominal and vaginal hysterectomy becomes an essential step to strengthen patient safety, optimize decision-making, and move toward institutional practices aligned with international standards. Furthermore, this information will support the implementation of training programs in vaginal hysterectomy, a strategy backed by organizations such as the American College of Obstetrical and Gynecologists

(ACOG) and the World Health Organization (WHO), which emphasize the importance of continuous training and technical standardization to reduce operative variability and improve postoperative results.

Added to this situation is the absence of a local registry that systematically documents the frequency and type of complications according to the surgical route employed. Without this information, the service lacks objective evidence to evaluate institutional results, compare the safety of different approaches, and justify the implementation of improvement strategies, such as training programs in vaginal techniques or surgical selection protocols.

Therefore, there is an urgent need to comparatively analyze the complications associated with abdominal and vaginal hysterectomy at the General Hospital of Cancun, with the purpose of generating local evidence to identify risks, recognize opportunities for improvement, and guide decision-making toward safer, more efficient practices in line with international standards.

METHODOLOGY

This is an observational, retrospective, comparative, and cross-sectional study with a quantitative approach. Clinical records of all patients who underwent total abdominal or vaginal hysterectomy between January and December 2024 were analyzed. Non-probabilistic convenience sampling was used, including only cases that met the defined criteria.

Data were obtained through the review of physical and digital clinical records and organized in an electronic matrix. Basic descriptive and comparative statistics were applied. Variables recorded included: age, type of surgery, and postoperative complications.

This work was reviewed and evaluated by the Hospital's Research Committee (CI-2025-057-HGC) and Research Ethics Committee (CEI-2025-057-HGC). The study involved no risk to patients, as it was based on a documentary review. Information was handled confidentially and anonymized, taking necessary measures to protect patient identity and removing any identifying data.

RESULTS

The initial distribution was established according to the surgical route—abdominal and vaginal—with a total of 78 cases; subsequent exclusions due to incomplete records or absence of essential clinical data were identified. Figure 1 shows the transition from the initial group to the final group of 67 patients included in the analysis, as well as the nature and frequency of documented complications for each surgical route.

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Figure 1. Participant selection process.

SOURCE: Own elaboration.

Of the total distribution of the 67 patients included in the study, it was identified that 92.5% of the procedures were performed via the abdominal route (Graph 1).

Graph 1. Total distribution of patients according to surgical route.

SOURCE: Own elaboration.

Table 1 presents the differences in the type and frequency of complications between abdominal and vaginal hysterectomies. In the abdominal hysterectomy group (n=62), 7 complications were documented, representing 11.29% of the total procedures performed via this route. The most frequent complications were bladder injury, urinary

incontinence, and one vesicovaginal fistula, which represented the only serious event recorded in this group. Despite being the most utilized approach, the majority of abdominal procedures were completed without complications (55 cases), reflecting an acceptable rate of relative safety.

Table 1. Complications identified according to surgical route.

Type of Complication	Abdominal (n=62)	Vaginal (n=5)
Bladder injury	3	0
Urinary incontinence	3	0

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Vesicovaginal fistula	1	0
Hematoma	0	1
Urinary retention	0	1
Total complications	7 (11.29%)	2 (40%)
Without complications	55	3

SOURCE: Own elaboration.

Although the number of vaginal hysterectomies was considerably lower (n=5), this group presented two complications, equivalent to a proportion of 40%, which is notably higher than that observed in the abdominal route. The identified complications were: postoperative hematoma and urinary retention. This high proportion should be interpreted with caution, as the small sample size may magnify the percentage impact of each event. Nonetheless, it suggests that, in this group, the rate of adverse events was proportionally higher. Overall, the table analysis shows that while abdominal

hysterectomies account for a higher absolute number of complications due to the volume of procedures, the vaginal route presents a higher proportional risk. This difference highlights the importance of considering both absolute numbers and percentages adjusted to the size of each group when evaluating the safety of each surgical technique. Regarding the variables of age and type of procedure, the group between 41–50 years of age presented the highest number of complications, with 9 recorded for abdominal hysterectomy and 1 for the vaginal route (Graph 2).

Graph 2. Complications by age range: Abdominal vs. Vaginal route.

SOURCE: Own elaboration.

DISCUSSION

Analyzing the complications occurring in both the abdominal and vaginal routes, the literature indicates that the appearance of intra- and postoperative complications depends on the type of approach, body mass index, and surgical experience, highlighting that the vaginal route and minimally invasive techniques offer better outcomes when clinically viable (5).

In the national context, it is reported that while there is a growing trend toward the use of laparoscopic techniques, the abdominal route still represents around 39% of cases and is associated with a complication rate of 10%, higher than that observed in vaginal and laparoscopic approaches (3).

According to the analysis performed for this hospital, similar figures were not achieved, as the analyzed data evidenced that the vaginal route had the highest number of complications. However, this is not a reliable indicator given that in our study population, the vaginal approach was performed in only 5 patients; therefore, a much larger study population would be required for data reliability.

Hysterectomy presents risks that can manifest both during the surgical act and in the postoperative period. Described complications include hemorrhage, surgical site infection, urinary tract injury, bladder injury, pulmonary thromboembolism, urogenital fistulas, hypovolemic shock, ureteral obstruction, and visceral damage (2). The incidence

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of complications varies by surgical route; studies report global rates of 11.8% for the abdominal route, 12.3% for the vaginal route, and 14% for the laparoscopic route (2).

In the abdominal approach, the most frequent complications are vaginal vault abscess, wound infection, and vesicourinary injury (2), according to the consulted literature; however, with the results obtained, the most frequent complication was urinary injury. In the case of vaginal hysterectomy, early postoperative hemorrhage is relatively more common, generally associated with bleeding from the uterine artery or vaginal angles (7, 8). None of the

complications described in the literature occurred in any patient in our analysis.

The identification of risk factors allows for an understanding of why some patients have a higher probability of developing complications following a hysterectomy. These clinical, surgical, and institutional elements have been consistently documented in the literature and help contextualize the outcomes observed in different populations. Table 2 synthesizes the main factors described in national and international studies, as well as their associated clinical impact.

Table 2. Risk factors associated with postoperative complications in hysterectomy.

Risk Factor	Description of Risk	Associated Clinical Impact
Maternal age \geq 45 years	Greater tissue fragility and more comorbidities	Increases bleeding, infection, and prolonged recovery
Obesity (BMI \geq 30)	Hinders technique and compromises healing	Higher risk of infection, seromas, dehiscence, and thrombosis
Chronic comorbidities (HTN, DM, anemia, heart disease)	Prior systemic compromise	High risk of hemorrhage, anesthetic complications, and thrombosis
Smoking	Affects microcirculation and tissue oxygenation	Infection, dehiscence, and delayed healing
Surgical technique (Abdominal vs. Vaginal)	Abdominal route is more invasive	Higher morbidity compared to the vaginal route
Procedure duration (> 60 min)	Prolonged surgeries reflect technical difficulty	More bleeding, infections, and anesthetic events
Institutional limitations	Lack of technology and training in less invasive techniques	Predominance of abdominal route and increased complications

SOURCE: Own elaboration based on references (2, 5).

The table demonstrates that patient-related factors—such as age over 45 years, obesity, and chronic comorbidities—significantly increase the probability of bleeding, infection, and recovery difficulties, regardless of the type of approach. This coincides with international literature, where systemic fragility and the presence of chronic diseases are consistently associated with higher postoperative morbidity. At the General Hospital of Cancun “Dr. Jesús Kumate Rodríguez,” technological availability, the absence of specialized equipment, and the lack of formal training in vaginal techniques have generated a pattern in which the abdominal route is used routinely, even in cases where the vaginal route would be feasible and potentially safer. This practice not only increases postoperative morbidity but also prolongs hospital stays, increases the demand for institutional resources, and exposes patients to avoidable complications.

The current situation, where only one operator fully masters the technique and the complication rate reaches 40%, confirms the urgency of establishing a structured training process that reduces technical variability and allows for the

standardization of practice according to ACOG and WHO guidelines. This program offers an academic-operative model that integrates theoretical training, simulator practice, supervised surgeries, competency certification, and continuous monitoring, ensuring that every professional acquires the necessary skills to perform vaginal hysterectomy safely and reproducibly.

The implementation of an Institutional Training Program in Vaginal Hysterectomy represents a strategic and necessary action to strengthen the surgical capacity of the Gynecology Service and improve the safety of patients treated at the General Hospital of Cancun “Dr. Jesús Kumate Rodríguez.” Scientific evidence is consistent in demonstrating that the vaginal route is the safest, most efficient, and cost-effective approach when surgical personnel possess the appropriate competencies.

By executing this intervention, the institution will not only decrease complications and improve clinical outcomes but also consolidate its role as a training center, strengthen the quality of gynecological care, and promote a culture of safety and continuous updating. This proposal constitutes a

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decisive step toward a more efficient, modern surgical practice aligned with international standards.

Table 3. List of activities to be performed for vaginal hysterectomy training.

Activity	Description
Preparation	Appoint a gynecologist tutor, form an operations team, and validate the institutional protocol.
Theoretical training	Educational sessions: indications, anatomy, surgical technique, and complication management.
Simulator training	Practice on anatomical pelvis: colpotomy, hemostasis, uterine extraction, and advanced maneuvers.
Supervised surgeries	Patient selection, case scheduling, and performance of at least 3 supervised surgeries per physician.
Feedback	Post-case analysis, technique correction, and individualized adjustments.
Internal certification	Final performance evaluation and accreditation as a competent operator.
Monitoring	Monthly review of complications, surgical times, and protocol audit.
Program consolidation	Integrate the course into the annual plan, update the protocol, and expand the number of trained operators.

SOURCE: Own elaboration.

CONCLUSION

Most comparative studies have demonstrated that the vaginal route presents better outcomes in terms of safety, lower complication rates, shorter surgical times, and shorter hospital stays compared to the abdominal route (2). In one retrospective study, 100% of the identified complications occurred in the abdominal route, with vaginal vault abscess and wound infection being the predominant complications. Likewise, the laparoscopic route has shown lower rates of infection and readmission, although its availability is conditioned by specialized training (6).

Recent studies consistently indicate that the abdominal route concentrates a higher proportion of postoperative complications. Postoperative complications for both abdominal and vaginal routes should be interpreted with caution, as the small sample size may magnify the percentage impact of each event. Nonetheless, it suggests that, in this group, the rate of adverse events was proportionally higher. Overall, the data analysis shows that while abdominal hysterectomies account for a higher absolute number of complications due to the volume of procedures, the vaginal route presents a higher proportional risk. This difference highlights the importance of considering both absolute numbers and percentages adjusted to the size of each group when evaluating the safety of each surgical technique.

Despite significant advances in international literature, important gaps remain. Most studies are conducted in private institutions or high-specialty centers, which limits their applicability in general hospitals with restricted resources. Furthermore, few works analyze the role of surgical training, inter-operator variability, and the institutional impact of adopting less invasive routes— aspects that are critical in contexts such as the General Hospital of Cancun. Finally, there is still a scarcity of local comparative studies documenting the actual frequency of

complications according to the surgical route used, which hinders the implementation of evidence-based protocols.

Intervention Proposal: Based on the results obtained, an institutional proposal will be formulated as presented in Table 3, including:

- Development of an internal surgical selection protocol based on local clinical factors.
- Staff training in vaginal hysterectomy.
- Implementation of a standardized preoperative format.
- Presentation of results to the Quality Committee to guide continuous improvement processes.

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